

FORMATION OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP MOTIVATION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF LABOR EDUCATION IN THE FAMILY

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Annotation. *This article discusses the formation of entrepreneurial motivation through labor education in the family, ensuring the success of the entrepreneurial movement, the pedagogical system of developing entrepreneurial skills in students, the economic competence of developing entrepreneurial skills in the family.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, family entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial motivation, "teacher-student" traditions, economist, young entrepreneur, entrepreneurial qualities, economic competence, entrepreneurial motivation.*

Introduction. Within the framework of the State Program "Youth is our Future", a number of reforms are being implemented in the country to direct students to entrepreneurship, to develop family business, to develop entrepreneurial skills in students on the basis of school and family cooperation. At the same time, there is a need to develop a pedagogical model and integrative technology for the development of entrepreneurial skills in students on the basis of school-family cooperation, to improve the system of targeted vocational training of students based on the tradition of "teacher-student". The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan identifies important tasks such as "creating a favorable business environment for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, creating conditions for the full realization of labor and entrepreneurial activity of the working population, involvement in private entrepreneurship." This requires the identification of components, criteria, pedagogical and psychological features, didactic opportunities for the development of entrepreneurial skills in the family, the improvement of the pedagogical system for the development of entrepreneurial skills in students.

The main part. The transition to a market economy has raised the issue of increasing the economic knowledge of the population, especially young people, and the formation of innovative thinkers - entrepreneurs. That is why today the number of family entrepreneurs and small

businesses in our country is growing and the demand for them is growing. This, of course, requires the training of representatives of the industry, the development of educational work to educate young people in the spirit of entrepreneurship. In our opinion, it is advisable to start this process from the family, the main link in society. The main goal of labor education and upbringing in primary school is not only to provide economic knowledge to young people, but also to develop in them entrepreneurial skills based on the economic and market requirements of society. Because in order to solve this problem, the development of modern and innovative technologies, methods and techniques of entrepreneurship education in primary education should be reflected in today's pedagogical research. Therefore, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has always said about the development and support of entrepreneurship: "Freedom of entrepreneurial activity, ensuring the inviolability of private property will continue to be a priority in public policy. We will continue to pursue a policy of further liberalizing our economy and opening the way for entrepreneurs. As the head of state, I will always pay close attention to the issue of supporting this crucial sector and completely removing the obstacles that lie ahead. "

In our country, within the framework of the State Program "Youth - Our Future", a number of reforms are being implemented to direct students to entrepreneurship, to develop family business, to develop entrepreneurial skills in students on the basis of school-family cooperation. At the same time, there is a need to develop a pedagogical model and integrative technology for the development of entrepreneurial skills in students on the basis of school-family cooperation, to improve the system of targeted vocational training of students based on the tradition of "teacher-student". The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan identifies important tasks such as "creating a favorable business environment for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, creating conditions for the full realization of labor and entrepreneurial activity of the working population, involvement in private entrepreneurship." This requires the identification of components, criteria, pedagogical and psychological features, didactic opportunities for the development of entrepreneurial skills in the family, the improvement of the pedagogical system for the development of entrepreneurial skills in students.

Entrepreneurship development and growth requires the development of entrepreneurial skills in primary education and the

acquisition of basic knowledge, skills and competencies. Before talking about this, it is useful for students to be introduced to the concepts of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship. Because in today's world, the word "entrepreneur" refers to people who buy a product and then sell it at a premium. In fact, an entrepreneur is not a seller, but, as noted in the Uzbek Dictionary, an entrepreneur is a person who organizes, finances, manages a commercial or industrial enterprise for profit. The glossary also defines "entrepreneurship" as an entrepreneurial behavior, activity, or quality. Through such explanations from the teacher, students learn that the entrepreneur is not just a salesman, but a resourceful, resourceful and enterprising person. Today, according to the basic curriculum of general secondary schools, in grades 1-4, "Mother tongue", "Reading", "Etiquette", "Mathematics", "The world around us", "Technology" The course "Alphabet of Economics and Taxation" is taught. The main purpose of this course is to teach students the basics of economics from an early age, to form the concept of entrepreneurship, to explain the ongoing economic reforms in the country, small business and private entrepreneurship, taxes and their types with simple examples. As the teacher teaches the students, they learn about mental and physical labor, about entrepreneurs, business people, money, the use of money, seller and buyer, trade, market, income, profit, tax, production, begins to form initial concepts such as price-navo.

These concepts are explained by the parent in the family or the older generation in the family. It is very useful for the family to know the market price for the child. The parent explains to the child the daily (or weekly) results of the market price. At the same time, in technology classes at school, students can try to prepare household items (if possible, sell them) and create the necessary conditions for entrepreneurship. .

A study of the economic nature of the concept of "family business" provides some insights. In particular, M.K.Pardaev and Z.N.Kurbanov defined the concept of family business as follows: "Entrepreneurship with the participation of family members based on family property is called family business."

G.Shodieva defines this economic concept as the main purpose of family members in entrepreneurship, as follows: "Family entrepreneurship is based on family property, in which family members participate and to a certain extent income (profit) activities that seek to obtain."

A.Muxsieva, a researcher of the methodological bases of the national process of family upbringing, in her research said that in the process of

family upbringing, on the basis of entrepreneurship and rational economic management, children can develop such qualities as nationalism, thrift, organization, initiative, resourcefulness, intelligence, responsibility and entrepreneurship. "Market relations require children to acquire a thorough knowledge of economics in the family and in educational institutions, to develop in them the skills and abilities to organize economic activities, including family farming. In the current context of economic reforms, it is necessary not only to ensure the spiritual and moral development of children, but also to ensure that they become thrifty and entrepreneurial in the management of the economy.

Conclusion. Developing entrepreneurial skills in the family is one of the key components of economic competence. Therefore, the development of entrepreneurship in students should be considered as an integral part of the educational process. In order to develop entrepreneurial motivation in young people in the family, it is advisable to take into account the following: preliminary assessment of their abilities; distribution of youth labor according to its strength; talent promotion; demanding

Each member of the family is not only a family farmer, but also an active participant in production in the country. Therefore, today one of the most important social tasks is to bring up children brought up in a family environment as entrepreneurs, along with the family farm. Entrepreneurship management can help young people develop such qualities as nationalism, thrift, resourcefulness, intelligence and entrepreneurship.

The results of the study of the family environment in childhood, which influences the preparation of students for entrepreneurial activity, were more meaningful, and it was found that the parents of most entrepreneurs were artisans. Most families with both fathers and mothers are entrepreneurs. It is clear that parental influence on student choice of entrepreneurial activity is large. Entrepreneurs have a great reputation for their activities and goals. They are loyal to their work. Information is being disseminated to encourage young entrepreneurs to mobilize all their resources to ensure the success of the business movement and to achieve the goals they have set for themselves. A positive attitude towards entrepreneurship affects the life, lifestyle and personality of the entrepreneur.

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